

RESEARCH

VUCA Impact Of Covid-19 On Marketing Of Two-wheeler In Rural And Urban Markets Of India

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ABSTRACT

VUCA i.e. Volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity, is the best word that describes the current situation arising out of the COVID-19 pandemic. But it is interesting to note that despite the gloom, things are looking optimistic. The marketers of Two-wheeler are argue, that things will normalize soon. They believe that the negative repercussions of the pandemic are estimated to be short lived and may last for a few months. They believe that in the long run, the Corona effect will lead to a major boost in the sales figures of Two-wheeler.

The research undertaken is unique as it deals with a phenomenon never experienced before. The earlier research studies were related to consumer buying behaviour for Two-wheeler. These research studies were limited to the profile of the consumers, their expectations, satisfaction level and the features of the Two-wheeler. This research undertaken provides a holistic picture of the Two-wheeler industry in era of COVID-19 crises. The research is of great significance as the automobile sector of the country is considered to be one of the most vibrant and happening industry in the country.

The study and its findings will lead to congruence of marketing strategies of Two-wheeler companies and customer expectations. It will also help in seeking the much required support from policy makers in the government by bringing to their notice the plight of the automobile sector with the advent of COVID-19 situation. The paper aims to influx positivity in the minds of the marketers and make them feel optimistic about the new normal. It proposes that despite the big blow, the economy of the country has taken, especially the industrial sector, things are not that bad for the Two-wheeler industry.

The study will give a new dimension to the way the manufacturers of the automobile industry view the market. The research will highlight reasons for the demand that is likely to unfold in future. The researcher also intend to give satisfactory reasons why some companies had increased sales in 2020 as compared to the corresponding months of 2019 in the previous year. The study based on exhaustive research of available secondary data aims to examine the marketing strategies of six major Two-wheeler companies during the unlock phase. The six companies that are considered

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for the study are Hero Moto Corp, Honda, TVS, Bajaj Auto, Yamaha and the Royal Enfield. These six companies were considered due to their significant market share and the brand value they command in the Indian market. The combined market share of these six companies accounts for more than 95 percent share of the Two-Wheeler market.

The period of the study is from January 2018 to November 2020. The sales figures of the six leading Two-wheeler manufacturing companies for the year 18/19 and 2020 were considered for the study. A comparison of the sales figures of 2019 and 2020 for each month was done so as arrive at a conclusion. Appropriate percent increase and decrease in sales are highlighted.

Appropriate tables and graphs that depict sales figures for the current year (2020) and previous two years (2018 /2019) are considered so that the hypothesis that is framed can be tested and the objectives of the study are achieved. The study makes a comparison of sales figures between the months post the unlock phase for the current year i.e. 2020. An attempt has also been made to compare the market share of companies and the positive / negative impact on sales of the COVID-19 pandemic on the six companies considered for the study. An analysis for the increase or decrease in the market share has been done to as to suggest suitable remedies. A proper SWOT analysis of the existing situation will help in giving new insights on how to sail through the existing situation and make the most of the opportunity.

The important reasons why sales of Two-wheeler are likely to increase are, people will avoid the public transport system and may opt for the Two-wheeler mode of transportation as it is very economical and convenient, many employees have faced salary deductions and hence for the time being, they will avoid buying a car and instead buy a two wheeler. Many women who till date did not think of buying a Two-wheeler for self-use, will now consider buying one, this will include house wives, who need to venture out of their homes to fulfill many domestic obligations. Many Two-wheeler manufacturing companies are making loan options more simplified to make things easy for the buyers during times of financial crisis. Home delivery of goods has increased, so companies in the business of delivering goods to customers like Swiggy, Zomato Domino's and courier companies may indulge in placing orders for bulk purchases for their employees. Post the pandemic it is estimated that Two-wheeler service taxi may be the new lucrative business, resulting in more demand for Two-wheeler.

The rural markets of the country may also see a boost in sales of Two-wheeler as the country has witnessed a more than satisfactory rainfall resulting in good harvest by the farmers. The special COVID relief funds may increase the surplus of cash. The loan waivers announced by the government will increase the level of motivation among the rural folks. Companies are well aware that aspirations of rural consumers are on the rise due to rising incomes, educational levels and the increasing penetration of television and internet.

KEYWORDS: VUCA, COVID-19, pandemic, lockdown, unlock, Two-wheeler.

INTRODUCTION:

India is the world's largest two wheeler markets. In the year 2016, it raced ahead of China in terms of Two-wheeler sales for domestic consumption. The Two-wheeler industry is the backbone of the automobile sector of the country and accounts for approximately 80 percent share of the country's automobile sector. The Indian automobile industry makes a significant contribution of 7.1 percent to the GDP of the country. The share of the automobile sector in the GST revenues is 15 percent. More than 35 million people seek direct or indirect employment in the automobile sector. The contribution of the automobile sector to the exports of the country is around 4.3 percent of the total exports, which is quite significant. The automobile sector has helped in attracting FDIs to the tune of 2.82 billion U.S dollars in form of equity inflows (Keelery, 2020).

The COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 had a huge impact on the Two-wheeler industry and consequently on the automobile sector of the country. The lockdown announced all of a sudden by the government almost brought to a halt the manufacturing and sales of Two-wheeler. Never before has the Two-wheeler industry, experienced crisis of such magnitude. There is uncertainty among businesses, employees and the society at large. Salary deductions, loss of jobs and income are common. The paper makes a detailed analysis of the hard times faced by

the manufacturers of Two-wheeler during the lock down. It also analyses the struggles of the companies post the lockdown and the efforts made to overcome the obstacles.

The Two-wheeler mode of transportation is quite popular in India. Most Indians as young kids learn to ride a cycle, so the switch over to a Two-wheeler is an upgradation which is rather very smooth, easy and fun. The market for Two-wheelers is vast, especially for a country like India which has a huge population and approximately 60 percent of its population is below 30 years of age. The young Indian population is a clear indication that Two-wheeler manufacturing companies have either potential customers or have future prospective customers (population below 17 years of age). Riding a Two-wheeler is the dream and passion of most youth especially the male. Many Two-wheeler companies have launched attractive models with unique features to appeal to the youth. Two-wheeler are available in three main categories i.e. motorbikes, scooters and mopeds. The motorbikes are popular with the young male segment, a scooter is popular with both the genders i.e. male and female, but more so with the female gender and the middle aged males and mopeds are generally used by people with low income groups as they are less priced, and considered more fuel efficient. A Two-wheeler is the most common personal means of transportation in the country.

Source: <https://indiancompanies.in>.

More than 60 percent of the country's population resides in rural areas. The population is scattered and spread across approximately 625000 big or small villages. People residing in rural India; buy a Two-wheeler more as necessity rather than a luxury. The necessity for buying a Two-wheeler arises due to number of factors like, lack of good public transport facilities, narrow lanes through which cars or other four wheeled vehicles cannot be navigated, lack of motor able roads, lack of basic supplies / health care / education in the locality they reside etc. A Two-wheeler which is affordable serves as the best answer to the issue of transportation. People in urban localities need a Two-wheeler for a variety of reasons like a two wheeler can be easily maneuvered in traffic, ease in parking, fuel economy, good for short distance travel etc. The number of working women is higher in cities and towns, so the demand for non-g geared vehicles users will be higher in cities and towns.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Promod Patil (2017) in his research paper titled "Rural and Urban consumer of India"

the author explains that the concept of rural marketing in the country is still a concept that is evolving despite the fact that most of our population resides in the rural area of the country. The study was undertaken with the objective of understanding the rural and urban consumers and to discuss the differences in marketing in rural and urban markets. In the study it was proposed that the rural consumer indulges in rational buying, intends value for his money, rural consumer is a rational decision maker, his buying is need based and the decision making process is consensus based where family members and opinion leaders are involved. The study was based on secondary data which was collected from thesis, reports, books, journals and newspapers. The study concludes that rural consumers are homogeneous and the rural society is rigid. The urban population is concentrated, but rural population is scattered and hence issues related to distribution may arise.

Ronald Mani and Dr. Debasis Tripathy (2016) in their research work titled "A Study on Consumer Buying Behaviour towards Two

Wheeler Bikes in context to Indian Market” explains that buying behaviour of the Indian consumer is influenced by social, cultural, personal and psychological factors. The study was conducted in the cities of Allahabad, Varanasi and Lucknow in the state of Uttar Pradesh. The conclusions of the study were; there is high demand for Honda bikes and the company needs to improve the supply, mileage of Honda and Yamaha needs improvement, Hero needs to redesign its bikes to make it more attractive, the price of Yamaha is high so company needs to work towards reducing the price of the vehicle and Bajaj Two-wheelers focus only on the youth, the company needs to consider the middle aged group. The study concludes that Bajaj and Honda were the best on customer satisfaction level.

Ms. Priyanka Jain (2015) in her research titled “A Study of Customer Satisfaction of Two Wheelers on Yamaha”. The main objective of the study was to understand the customer satisfaction level of Yamaha bike users. The researcher states that customer satisfaction for Yamaha bikes is high on all factors, except mileage. Youth is the target market for Yamaha bikes. The bikes are highly appreciated for their performance and design. The researcher in her study has proposed that aggressive promotions need to be undertaken to increase sales. She also cautions that looks and style must not lead to compromise on quality and mileage. In the research it was found that after sales service was not up to the expected standards. Friends acted as major influencers in consumer buying decisions. According to the findings of the study, there was dissatisfaction regarding the availability of the bikes during the actual delivery of the vehicle. The data for the study undertaken was collected from a sample of 100 respondents

who were users of Yamaha bikes. Dr. Sardar Gugloth & Margani Soma Sekhara (2012) in their research study titled “A Study relating to the decision – making Process of Purchasing Two-Wheeler's in rural area of Andhra Pradesh” propose that there is a huge demand for Two-wheeler in rural areas of the country. They explain that factors like mileage have significance impact on the decision making process. They further state that family and friends exert great influence on the buying behaviour of the rural consumer. In the research paper it was concluded that rural consumers do not have much access to information and hence cannot indulge in comparative studies, the marketers therefore need to design marketing strategies accordingly. The study was undertaken in Tamballapalli Taluka of Chittoor district. Data for the study was collected through a questionnaire from 96 respondents. The data collected clearly indicated that educational levels were low and for most respondents agriculture was the main source of income. It also indicated that a high number of respondents (80 percent) had income levels below rupees 150000 per annum.

Subrato Dey (2017) in his research titled “A Study on Changing Buying Behaviour of Indian Customers” explains that internet penetration and drastic increase in the use of social media has resulted in drastic change in the buying behaviour of Indian consumers. The study undertaken was based on consumer perception, their buying behaviour and consumer satisfaction. The objectives of the study were to understand different consumer types, their decision making process and the factors which affect their buying behaviour. The findings of the study were that Indian consumers are value oriented and even high end brands have to design a pricing strategy

that is unique. Consumer involvement is more when the product is expensive. The researcher has recommended that when buying, the consumers check what competitors are offering. Family and friends have a big influence on buying decisions and reviews of the product can influence buying decisions of the customers.

Basha S. Suraj; Dr. Laxshmanna B.C in their research “A Study on Factors Influencing Consumers Buying Behavior of Two wheelers with special reference to Rayalaseema region, Andhra Pradesh, India” The objectives of the study were to study factors that influence consumer buying behaviour and the impact of demographic factors on the consumers. The study was based both on primary and secondary data, with more focus on the secondary data. The period considered for the study was July 2016 to January 2017. The primary data was collected from 220 respondents from four towns of Rayalaseema region. There was a good representation of the male and female respondents in the sample for the study. The researchers in their findings state that consumer buying behavior is impacted by various factors like personal factors, psychological factors, social factors and cultural factors.

Vijayalakshmi D, ShanthaKumari M, Deepika S, in their research study titled “A Study of Customer Satisfaction of a Selected Branded Two Wheeler in South Coimbatore”. The study was conducted on five major two wheeler brands. The objectives of the study were to access the profile of Two-wheeler users, to know the association between socio economic profile and the brand purchased and to analyse the level of customer satisfaction. Data for the study was collected from 250

respondents, comprising of 50 respondents for each brand considered for the study. The authors conclude that most of the consumers felt the price of the two wheelers was high; most of the respondents came to know about the two wheelers through television advertisements. Consumers expect facilities like mobile charger, baby carrier. Matching helmets can be given. They feel that complaints should be addressed immediately Malla Riya in her research “Factors Affecting Brand Preference of Scooters among Women Consumers in Kathmandu Valley”. The data for the study was collected from 200 female scooter users. The respondents were from different homogeneous groups. The main objective of the study was to analyse the consumer preference for scooter in Khatmandu valley. The researcher has concluded that Hero has the highest brand preference, Honda is the second most sought after brand among women in Khatmandu valley. According to her findings there is no significant relationship between demographic variables and preference of scooters. Comfort and mileage are respectively the most important factors considered while choosing the brand of the scooter. It also states that there is no significant relationship between education and brand preference of scooters.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- To understand the impact and repercussions of COVID-19 pandemic on Two-wheeler manufacturing companies.
- To analyse the marketing strategies of Two-wheeler manufacturing companies during the unlock phase and give suitable suggestions.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The study was conducted using the available secondary data. Data was collected from

websites of companies, internet and newspaper reports. A thorough review of related literature was also done to collect information useful to the study undertaken. The domestic Sales of six leading Two-wheeler manufacturing companies before and after the COVID-19 pandemic were considered for the study.

DATA ANALYSIS:

Secondary data from authentic sources used for the research study. The sales figure reports collected were tabulated and analysed. The simple percentage method and t-test were used to arrive at a conclusion.

HYPOTHESIS:

The Study is undertaken with the following Hypothesis

Ho: There is no impact of COVID-19 on the sales of Two-wheeler.

Ha: There is an impact of COVID-19 on the sales of Two-wheeler.

Major Players in the Indian Two-wheeler Industry

Hero Moto Corp is the leading manufacturer of Two-wheeler in the country. The company till date has sold over 90 million Two-wheelers; it has over 6000 customer touch points and has been in business for more than 34 years. The company manufactures both geared and non-geared vehicles i.e. Scooter. Bajaj Auto is the world's third largest manufacturer of motorcycles. Bajaj Auto is an Indian company established in 1944. The company has approximately 660 dealers

across the country. The company has Two-wheeler bikes positioned for different price segments. Honda started its business operations in the country in the year 2001 and is one of the youngest players in the Two-wheeler market. Due to its consistency in giving quality products it has become the second largest Two-wheeler company in India with over 46 million customers. TVS motors are the third largest Two-wheeler manufacturer in India. It has the unique distinction of manufacturing the largest range of Two-wheelers. Their range of manufacturing includes motorcycles, scooters and mopeds. The company boasts of production capacity of 4.95 million Two-wheelers annually. The scooters manufactured by the company are very popular across all demographic variables in India. The bikes of Yamaha are a craze among the youth. The company is considered to have created India's most revolutionary Two-wheeler vehicle. The Yamaha R15 model is a rage among the youth. The bikes of the company are rated highly on aspects of technology, but score low on aspects of mileage and cost. The focus of Yamaha Company is on manufacturing the deluxe motorbikes and scooters. The Royal Enfield bikes are quite popular across the country for their power and sturdiness. Royal Enfield is one of the oldest motorcycle brands in the country that is still operational and continues to manufacture and launch new models of bikes for the bike lovers. The bikes of Royal Enfield are considered grand and royal. They are positioned for machoism due to their rugged looks, power and sturdiness.

Strategies adopted post COVID-19

Despite the VUCA impact, the Two-wheeler industry is expected to register a 16 percent to 18 percent sales growth as compared to the previous year Two-wheeler sales. The economy initially was severely affected due to COVID-19. The rating agencies had earlier estimated a decline of 11 percent to 13 percent in sales. In the initial stages, manufacturing and sales initially took a big hit, and almost all companies reported losses in the first few months. In the post lockdown period things gradually started to normalize and the sales as expected are rapidly picking up. It is for sure; people will now avoid the public transport to maintain social distancing and will now get more personalized in their mode of transport, being independent is the new norm. The disrupted public transport will further encourage buying of two wheelers. As per research report 33 percent of the respondents in a survey felt two wheeler were the safest mode of transport during COVID-19 times. Reduced income due cut in wages, high maintenance cost of cars, the four wheeled drive is a difficult option in the present

circumstances and hence the focus will be on buying a two wheeler. The recent sales figures of most Two-wheeler companies give clear indications of consumer demand revival.

Hero Moto Corp

The company is estimated to sell at least two in every five Two-wheelers sold in the country. The company has posted a growth of 35 percent in the month of October 2020. As per company reports, it is the highest ever sales in a single month. The concern for the company was that entry level vehicles contributed to a major share of the sales and it had very little contribution from the premium segment.

A survey by Hero Moto Corp indicated that the demand for two wheeler has increased from people who travel to work. As per reports, due to its rural reach, the company is expected to outperform its competitors in the coming months. The company increased its market share by 4.5 percent to 5 percent between the months of April to August 2020. In the month of June, 4.5 lakh units of

motorcycles and scooters were sold by the Hero Moto Corp. A major part of the sales of the company came from the rural and semi urban markets. A deep reach in the hinterlands and a number of low priced models have made this possible for the company. The first time buyers have fueled the sales growth. It is rather the need based buying of the consumers rather than the conventional buying reasons and logic. The scooter segment also registered a growth. The company made 95 percent of its customer touch point operational with due safety measures during the unlock phase. The management recently told its investors that supply was the main concern rather than demand. The company has plans to increase its sales in the international markets. The company has a strategy of launching premium segment bikes which are heftier and sporty to target the millennials. The company also plans to target the international markets with this premium model.

The company stated that forecast of a normal monsoon, a good Rabi crop and various revival packages by the government were instrumental in pushing the sales. The company is relying heavily on its rural demand. The rural consumers have always been inclined towards motorbikes. To meet the high demand, the company made wholesale deliveries to its dealer in record time, almost four times the dispatches the previous year.

In the month of November 2020, to boost sales of its electric Two-wheelers, the company has tied up with online platform CredR and as per the offer of the company customers can exchange their old petrol vehicles with new Hero electric Two-wheeler. Employees of CredR will make a valuation of the old Two-wheeler and fix a price tag to that.

The amount will be deducted on the purchase of the new electro Hero Two-wheeler. This offer is initially limited to a few Indian cities like, Poona, Delhi NCR, Hyderabad, Jaipur and Bangalore, and will be later extended all over the country in a gradual manner. The company is hopeful that this strategy will yield positive results during the unlock phase.

Honda

HMSI scooters contribute to 67 percent of the sales and motorcycles 33 percent, the same as pre COVID-19 times. The scooter segment is the main strength of the company. The company maintained its market position in the scooter segment with more than 50 percent of the market share. The rural consumption is on the rise as the urban markets were sluggish due to restrained economic activities and lockdowns. The company believes that sales of scooters particularly in rural areas will rise due to challenges of social distancing, increasing number of working women, unreliable public transport and the need for mobility thus creating a demand for two wheelers. The rate of enquiries turning into purchase has been high for the company (almost 40 percent). The company feels that individuals employed in the essential sectors like health and banking would be the likely buyers. Attractive EMIs with lower down payments have been worked out by the company.

Honda Company plans expansion in its premium bike segments, to overcome the havoc of the COVID-19 pandemic on its sales. The company has come up with innovative offers for its buyers. If payments are made with credit cards, the buyer can avail up to 95 percent loan and cash back. The cash back facility is 5 percent. The company has tied up IDFC and HDFC. The loan facility

will be for 36 months. The scheme is only for a few select dealers of Honda.

TVS Motors

TVS Company registered a decline of 62 percent in the month of March 2020, due to the lockdown. It was more or less the same case with its rivals. Like many other companies to cut down on expenses, TVS announced a deduction of 20 percent on staff salaries at executive level till the end of October 2020. Most of the employees took a voluntary salary cut. Despite the trying times, the company engaged in host of welfare activities. The company manufactured and distributed over one million face masks in Tamil Nadu and Karnataka to health care workers and service providers in the essential service provider category. The company also distributed 3.2 lakh food packets. The company also had vehicles covering 3,800 villages to meet any emergencies. The company also developed a mobile app to meet any needs of its employees related to health or cash. The company announced various customer friendly initiatives. A toll free number was made available to customers which was available 24/7 for any assistance or queries.

The marketers of TVS are optimistic that this is a temporary phase. Focusing on international markets was growth strategy adopted by the company. In the domestic market, the company has launched a new campaign with Amitabh Bachchan and M.S. Dhoni. The management is highly enthusiastic that with acquisition of the British legacy brand Norton and a high end 200 cc brand Zeppelin new marketing opportunities await the company. In October 2020, the sales of the company grew by 22 percent. The exports of the company grew in

the month of September, as compared to its exports in the month of September last year.

Bajaj Auto

The company had a sales increase of 12 percent in the 125-150 CC segment in October 2020. The sales of Bajaj motorcycles had declined 26 percent in July 2020 as compared to last year. In the month of April the company had no sales. The earnings of Bajaj Auto picked up in the month of September 2020. Inventories have been stocked up to avoid any complications that may arise. It does not want its manufacturing to be dented, a clear indication of being optimistic of business happening in times to come. The company believes that gradually the business is coming back on tracks but the challenges ahead remain. The rise in sales is attributed to the need for personal mobility. The company expects the festive seasons to fuel the sales growth further. Exports will help in generating more revenues. The company started witnessing sales in the month of July. The sales of Pulsar were very encouraging in the month of October 2020. The overall sales in the month of October had increased by 18 percent as compared to the sales in the same month the previous year.

The company has plans to address the portfolio gaps in the domestic market. The festivals are likely to push up sales. The challenges on the supply side have been managed reasonably well by the company. The Pulsar model is highly successful and bankable to help company ride through the crises. The company exports to 79 countries globally. The company experienced great demand in overseas markets including Africa and Latin America. As per reports, the company's international markets are doing better than the domestic markets. The

reopening of schools and entertainment places may see a further revival in demand in the domestic markets. Increasing footfalls and inquiries at dealership is very encouraging sign for the company in the domestic market. The demand from rural areas of the country is likely to give a boost to its sales in the domestic market. The company hopes of government intervention post the festive season, as the demand is likely to go down once the festive seasons are over. The company has entered into a joint venture with Triumph to manufacture 300-700 CC bikes in the premium segment. These models are expected to be in the market in the year 2021.

India Yamaha Motor

Taking into account that the lockdown phase was a sensitive time the company immediately modified their communication on social media. During the worst phase of the COVID-19 pandemic the company looked at the ground reality from the perspective of sales, dealership network and consumers. The company refrained from pushing products on social media. The content was limited to safety, tips about bike care and updates related to service. To keep the audience engaged, Yamaha did some activities related to games and contests on social media. The focus of the company was on using Instagram. Taking into consideration the difficult situation, the company undertook some interesting initiative like extension of service during lockdown, contactless delivery, online booking etc. The focus of the company has completely shifted towards digital marketing. The company announced a special scheme for COVID-19 frontline warriors, so as to extend its support to the frontline warriors. Under the scheme the EMIs for the first three months were reduced by 50 percent. The scheme was

for the purchase of new Yamaha vehicles by the frontline workers. A tab was kept on the conversations about the brand so as to be aware of the challenges faced by customers and help out the customers within the capacity. When some of its dealers began reopening during the unlock phase, the company ensured that all norms were followed and there was utmost hygiene and safety measure at the dealers. The same was communicated to the customers on social media. In November the company registered sales growth for the fifth consecutive month.

Royal Enfield

Royal Enfield commands a major share in the premium segment bikes. Competition in this segment has intensified in urban cities with entry of new models from other established companies. The major demand for its vehicles is from rural India. The rural consumers account for approximately 50 percent of the sales of Royal Enfield bikes. The company was compelled to look at the digital world to engage its customers, as physical engagements were not possible amid the COVID-19 lockdown. Digital engagement is at an all-time high during the lockdown phase. The company has run a wide range of campaigns to bring the Royal Enfield community under one umbrella. The Trip Story was one of the few social media engagements undertaken by the company. According to reports, the company came up with the innovative idea of encouraging their customers, fans and enthusiastic to voluntarily share their stories. The initiative received an amazing response with use of platforms like Facebook. The brand has 40 lakh customers but over 70 lakh followers on digital platforms, an indication that its reach is beyond its customer base. After things are

back on track, diverse and huge number of potential customers awaits the range of models of Royal Enfield.

When restrictions on the lockdown were lifted, Royal Enfield announced contactless purchase and contactless service options for its customers. They initiated the safety on wheels initiative. Under this initiative the company has taken bike service to the door step of the customer. The company for this purpose has deployed 800 bikes with appropriate tool kit across its large dealer network in the country. The service includes scheduled maintenance service, minor repairs and a host of other facilities.

Post the lock down the demand for the bikes have shot up, but the supply is not up to the mark. The company is on a backlog of more than 40,000 bookings. The online enquiries for the bike have gone up almost five times, compared to the Pre-COVID-19 period. The demand is exciting for the company, but the inability to deliver has affected its moral in a big way. The company sold 60,000 bikes every month before the lockdown, the company is optimistic of higher sales when the supply related issues are sorted out.

Sales of Two-Wheeler in Domestic Market from Jan.to Nov. 2020

Company	Jan - March 2020	Apr- 2020	May- 2020	Jun- 2020	Jul- 2020	Aug. 2020	Sept. 2020	Oct. 2020	Nov. 2020	Total
Hero	1284950	0	112682	450744	506946	568674	697000	732498	575957	4929451
Honda	935115	0	54820	202837	321583	428231	500887	494459	412641	3350573
TVS	426796	0	41067	144817	189647	218338	241762	301380	247789	1811596
Bajaj	403084	0	39286	146695	152474	178220	219500	268631	188196	1596086
Yamaha	137296	0	11630	29539	49989	60505	63052	60176	53208	465395
Enfield	155110	91	18429	36510	37925	47571	55910	66891	59084	477521
Total	3342351	91	277914	1011142	1258564	1501539	1778111	1924035	1536875	2630622

Source : <https://www.rushlane.com/> <https://www.autopundit.com/>

Sales of Two-Wheeler in Domestic Market Jan. to Nov.2019

Company	Jan.-Sept	Oct. 19	Nov.19	Total 2019
Hero	5177092	599248	505994	6282334
Honda	3711706	487782	396366	4595854
TVS	2090755	252684	191222	2534661
Bajaj	1722522	242516	176337	2141375
Yamaha	519776	46082	39406	605264
Enfield	516504	67538	60411	644453
Total	13738355	1695850	1369736	16803941

The t-test was carried out to test the hypothesis. The period from January to November was considered for the years 2019 & 2020.

t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means

	Sale Jan. To Nov. 2019	Sale Jan. To Nov. 2020
Mean	2800656.833	2105103.667
Variance	5063835948548.57	3042209460665.47
Observations	6	6
Pearson Correlation	0.998340377	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Df	5	
t Stat	3.283926989	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.010929762	
t Critical one-tail	2.015048373	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.021859524	
t Critical two-tail	2.570581836	

The p value is significantly low at 0.022. In the test carried out $P < 0.05$ ($0.022 < 0.05$) so we reject the Null hypothesis and hence the alternative hypothesis is accepted i.e. there is an impact of COVID-19 on the sales of Two-wheeler.

Sale of Two-Wheeler in Domestic Market Jan. to Nov. 2018

Company	Jan.-Sept	Oct. 18	Nov.18	Total
Hero	6064816	716059	601045	7381920
Honda	4692518	490124	418367	5601009
TVS	2337840	338988	260253	2937081
Bajaj	1833675	281582	205259	2320516
Yamaha	609767	83379	60116	753262
Enfield	646573	70044	65744	782361
Total	16185189	1980176	1610784	19776149

Considering Two-wheeler sales figures for the Year 2018/2019/2020 from January to November we can easily conclude that sales in 2018 were higher as compare to 2019 and sales in 2019 were higher as compare to 2020. The decline in sales could be attributed to

economic cycles and the BS-VI norms made mandatory by Government for Two-wheeler manufactures. The COVID-19 impact had an effect on sales of Two-wheeler only during month of March, April and May 2020. Sales gradually started picking up from June 2020.

Sale of Two-Wheeler in Domestic Market Jan. to Nov. 2018

Company	June			July			August		
	2019	2020	% change YoY	2019	2020	% change YoY	2019	2020	% change YoY
Hero	6,16,526	4,50,744	-26.89%	5,11,374	5,06,946	-0.87%	5,24,003	5,68,674	8.52%
Honda	4,50,888	2,02,837	-55.01%	4,55,036	3,21,583	-29.33%	4,25,664	4,28,231	0.60%
TVS	2,26,279	1,44,817	-36.00%	2,08,489	1,89,647	-9.04%	2,19,528	2,18,338	-0.54%
Bajaj	1,99,340	1,46,695	-26.41%	1,70,978	1,52,474	-10.82%	1,73,024	1,78,220	3.00%
Yamaha	54,215	29,539	-45.51%	47,916	49,989	4.33%	52,704	60,505	14.80%
Enfield	55,082	36,510	-33.72%	49,182	37,925	-22.89%	48,752	47,571	-2.42%

Company	Sep			Oct			Nov		
	2019	2020	% change YoY	2019	2020	% change YoY	2019	2020	% change YoY
Hero	6,00,509	6,97,000	16.12%	5,52,672	7,32,498	32.54%	5,05,994	5,75,957	13.83%
Honda	4,55,896	5,00,887	9.87%	4,87,819	4,94,459	1.36%	3,73,283	4,12,641	10.54%
TVS	2,43,047	2,41,762	-0.53%	2,52,684	3,01,380	19.27%	1,91,222	2,47,789	29.58%
Bajaj	1,77,348	2,19,500	23.77%	2,42,516	2,68,631	10.77%	1,76,337	1,88,196	6.73%
Yamaha	53,727	63,052	17.36%	46,082	60,176	30.58%	39,406	53,208	35.03%
Enfield	54,858	55,910	1.92%	71,964	66,891	-7.05%	58,292	59,084	1.36%

Source: <https://www.rushlane.com>

Note: Lockdown restrictions were lifted gradually in the month of May 2020 and Companies and dealers resumes operations in phased manner. The data indicate a steady rise in sales every month. Due to festival season, the sales where in peak level in the month of October.

In the months of August, September, October and November the sales were higher in 2020 as compared to the sales in corresponding months of the previous year.

Market share (Domestic) of companies from June-November 2019/2020.

Two-Wheeler	Market share (June-Nov.) (%)	Market share (June- Nov.) (%)
Domestic	2019	2020
Hero	36	39
Honda	29	26
TVS	15	15
Bajaj	13	13
Yamaha	3	4
Enfield	4	3
	100	100

From the above table, it can be observed that sales of TVS and Bajaj remained unaffected due to COVID-19 Pandemic. There was a hike in sales of Hero and Yamaha Two-wheeler. Honda and Enfield (marginal) had decreased in sales in 2020 as compared to 2019.

The reasons for the decrease in sales of Honda and Enfield could be attributed to factors like; these companies do not have low priced models for the mass markets. (Entry level segment). Also post the pandemic rural areas accounted for a majority of the sales registered. Honda does not have a good rural reach in terms of dealer network and hence could not capitalize on the opportunity.

8.0 POST COVID-19 - SWOT Analysis of the Two-Wheeler Industry in India

The COVID-19 pandemic had a major negative impact on the sales of Two-wheeler in the month of March, April and May 2020. The industrial sector across the country suffered heavy losses and the Two-wheeler industry was no exception. For their survival, companies cut down on employee salaries and jobs.

In the month of June 2020 sales started showing an upward trend and gradually increased till the month of November 2020, it had almost caught up with the sales figures of the previous year 2019. Companies have learned the art of thriving in what is now the new normal. Two-wheeler manufacturers have realized the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats that are associated with the new normal.

<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Indian two wheeler industry is well established having been in the business for decades. • Two wheelers is already a popular mode of transport in the country. Most people comfortable with riding one. • Economic activities in rural areas not much affected. • Good monsoons, good harvests, cash inflows in forms of aid, farm loan waivers from government. • Economy slowly limping back to normalcy post lockdown. • Cut in corporate taxes. • Electric two wheelers gaining ground in India. 	<p>Weaknesses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Loss of income and jobs in the society. • Distribution (supply lines) severely disrupted. The distribution of vehicles to dealer outlets, inventories for production of goods affected. • Cost of fuel is already high. May see further escalation in future. • Higher income groups will opt for a car. • Banks already overburdened with bad debts. • Having reported revenue losses during lockdown, companies not in a position to offer freebies. • Due to the current situation, people may have other priorities that may put on hold buying a two wheeler.
<p>Opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most people reluctant to use public mode of transport. • New first time buyers in high numbers. • Rental two wheeler startups could be the new business ventures. • Online buying and delivery has drastically increased, hence scope for B2B sales for two wheeler companies. • Opportunities and scope for exploring international markets. • GST likely to be reduced on two wheelers as per indication from finance ministry. • Drastic increase in internet penetration. Scope for digital marketing increases multifold. 	<p>Threats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty of future as new wave of virus is predicted by experts. • Manufacturing cost may increase, resulting in overall price increase of the vehicle. • Some customer buying on loans may not be able to repay. • Work from home could be the new trend. • It is a wait and watch approach by most manufacturing sectors. Steps are taken with caution and risks avoided. • India is among the worst affected countries of the world. Business activities with India may be avoided by other countries i.e. Imports from India, Joint venture with Indian companies etc. • Due to uncertainty people may save money and avoid spending on a two wheeler.

CONCLUSIONS:

The COVID-19 pandemic had a significant impact on the sales of Two-wheeler in India. Companies like Hero Moto Corp and Yamaha have increased their market share. The increased market share of Hero has been quite impressive. The market share of Honda and Enfield has declined. TVS and Bajaj remained unaffected. Overall the road to recovery is long and may even play out like a game of snake and ladder. The market will throw up many first times buyers. Digital advertising will increase as more people are hooked up to mobile phones and increased penetration of internet. Two-wheeler companies had little or no sales during the months of April and May 2020, so most companies will try to indulge in aggressive marketing and promotional strategies to compensate for the loss of sales. The number of people buying on installment basis will see a drastic rise. Demand for Two-wheelers in rural India will be high. Most of the companies will now look to strengthen their exports. In the end it is concluded that despite all the challenges, pictures of proud owners of brand new two wheelers will be the uploaded more often on social media. The roads will witness brand new two wheelers navigating their way through the traffic.

SUGGESTIONS:

- Honda should think of launching motorcycles / scooters for the mass markets so as to compete with Hero, TVS and Bajaj which have models for the entry level segments.
- Enfield should tie up with financial institutions so as to encourage bike lovers to buy the model of their choice. The bikes of Enfield are popular in rural markets and hence it should focus more on rural

markets especially those that remain untapped.

- Companies instead of long term planning, should focus on short term plans, and have a plan B in place in case of any new challenges that suddenly arise.
- Front line warriors could be felicitated by the two wheeler dealers, and the most important contributors like doctors, nurses, policemen, could be provided with one free service or even a discount on purchase of two wheeler.
- Electric Two-wheeler does not even contribute to 1 percent of the share of Two-wheeler in the country. A creative and unique marketing strategy need to be adopted by companies for promoting electric Two-wheeler among the Indian consumers.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY:

- The study is based primarily on secondary data, supplemented by discussions with representatives of different groups.
- Data available till the month of November 2020 has been considered for the study.
- The representative of companies have made tall claims, the actual facts and figures will be uncovered only in due course of time.

IMPLICATIONS OF THE RESEARCH:

The study reflects the significant contribution of the Two-wheeler industry in the economic development of the country. The results of the study may act as an instrument to seek government intervention to bail out the automobile sector from the existing crisis. The research study will be a strong foundation and motivation for researchers, academicians and marketers to undertake more research activities related to automobile sector and

other consumer durables. It will also encourage more research work that is based on the available secondary data. This research paper will act as a platform on which further studies based on primary data could be conducted. Further studies could be carried out in 2021, so as to make comparisons with the scenario in 2020.

Region specific / company specific studies will help in giving more accurate results. Businesses and individuals are now gradually settling down in the new normal, a study after a gap of few months may throw up new results and outcomes.

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